

HISTORY AND EVOLUTION OF IR SYSTEM

INTRODUCTION

In 1952, Calvin Mooers coined the term 'information retrieval' and described it as "searching and retrieval of information from storage according to specific subject." This term gained popularity in the research community from 1961 onwards. At that point of time organizing function of information retrieval was a major progress in libraries. The libraries were no longer storehouses of books, but also places where the information was catalogued and indexed. Later, when computers were introduced in information handling, several bibliographic databases of documents were appeared, generally attached with abstracts, keywords, etc. Therefore, information retrieval turned up to retrieval of bibliographic information from stored document databases. Frankly speaking, these information retrieval systems were document retrieval systems, since they were designed to retrieve information about the existence (or non-existence) of documents relevant to a user query. Lancaster remarks that an information retrieval system does not inform the user on the subject of their enquiry, it merely informs them of the existence (or non-existence) and whereabouts of documents relating to their request. But this concept of information retrieval has changed because of the availability of full text documents in bibliographic databases. Modern information retrieval systems can either retrieve the exact text that matches a user's search criteria or bibliographic items from a stored database of full texts of documents. Even though information retrieval systems originally meant text retrieval systems, since they were dealing with textual documents, many modern information retrieval systems deal with multimedia information comprising text, image, video and audio. Although many features of conventional text retrieval systems are equally applicable to multimedia information retrieval, the specific nature of image, audio and video information have called for the development of many new tools and techniques for information retrieval. Modern information retrieval deals with organization, storage and access to text, as well as multimedia information resources.

INFORMATION RETRIEVAL

According to Larson (2011), "Information Retrieval (IR) is concerned with the storage, organization, and searching of collections of information."

According to Yates (1999), "Information retrieval (IR) deals with the representation, storage, organization of, and access to information items. The representation and organization of the information items should provide the user with easy access to the information in which he is interested."

INFORMATION RETRIEVAL SYSTEM

Information retrieval (IR), also called information storage and retrieval (ISR or ISAR) or information organization and retrieval, is the art and science of retrieving from a collection of items a subset that serves the user's purpose. [Soergel, 2004]

An information retrieval system is designed to analyse, process and store sources of information and retrieve those that match a particular user's requirements. [Chowdhury, 2004].

PURPOSE

An information retrieval system (IRS) is crafted to acquire the information or documents necessary for the user community. It should (ideally) present the correct information to the appropriate user. However, an IRS's purpose is to aggregate and categorize information across one or several subject areas, because it aims to deliver it to the user promptly upon request. Although efficiency is crucial, the system must also ensure the relevance of the information it provides. Belkin presents the following situation which clearly reflects the purpose of information retrieval systems:

1. A writer presents a set of ideas in a document using a set of concepts
2. Somewhere there will be some users who require the ideas but may not be able to identify those. In other words, there will be some persons who lack the ideas put forward by the author in his/her work

3. Information retrieval systems serve to match the writer's ideas expressed in the document with the users' requirements or demands for those.[Chowdhury,2004]

FUNCTIONS

Information retrieval system deals with various sources of information on the one hand and users' requirements on the other, It must:

- analyse the contents of the sources of information as well as the user queries and then
- match these to retrieve those items that are relevant

The major functions of an Information retrieval system can be listed as follows:

- identify the information sources relevant to the areas of interest of the target users' community
- to analyse the contents of the sources' documents
- to represent the contents of the analysed sources in a way that will be suitable for matching users' queries
- to analyse user queries and to represent them in a form that will be suitable for matching with the database
- to match the search statement with the stored database
- to retrieve the information that is relevant and
- to make necessary adjustments in the system based on feedback from the users

[Chowdhury,2004]

COMPONENTS

Lancaster mentions that an Information retrieval system comprises six major subsystems:

1. **Document Subsystem:** This component (which plays a crucial role) is responsible for the storage and management of a collection of documents or data sources upon which the information retrieval system operates. It encompasses processes related to document acquisition, storage and maintenance. The document subsystem (thus) ensures efficient access to

the indexed documents during retrieval; however, its effectiveness can be limited by various factors. Although it is designed to streamline access, there are times when efficiency is compromised because of external variables. This intricate interplay highlights the importance of robust management practices.

2. **Indexing Subsystem:** The indexing subsystem transforms documents into an index: a structured and searchable representation. It involves analysing the content of the documents; however, it also requires extracting relevant terms or features. Techniques, such as tokenization and stemming, may be employed to preprocess the papers and normalization can be crucial because this creates an index that facilitates efficient retrieval. Although the process may seem straightforward, it demands careful consideration of the specific characteristics of the documents involved.
3. **Vocabulary Subsystem:** The vocabulary subsystem (which is crucial) maintains a dictionary, or a vocabulary, of terms extracted from the indexed documents. It stores information regarding the frequency and location of terms in these documents. This subsystem is essential for mapping user queries to indexed terms; however, it also plays a significant role in efficiently retrieving relevant documents. Although it may seem straightforward, the complexity arises because of the intricate relationships between terms and their occurrences.
4. **Searching Subsystem:** The searching subsystem (which is crucial in information retrieval) processes user queries and retrieves relevant documents from the index. It involves various techniques: term matching, relevance ranking and result filtering. Although the subsystem focuses on efficiency, it also determines the most relevant documents based on the user's query, ranking algorithms and contextual factors. This process is essential for accurate results; however, the complexity of the algorithms can sometimes lead to unexpected outcomes.
5. **User-System Interface:** The user-system interface component offers a means for users to engage with the information retrieval system. It encompasses query input mechanisms, result displays and navigation options. This interface must be intuitive and user-friendly; however, it should also be capable of addressing diverse user queries and

preferences. Although it may seem straightforward, the complexity of user interactions can arise (because) of varying individual needs.

6. **Matching Subsystem:** The matching subsystem (which is integral to the overall architecture) executes the process of matching user queries with indexed documents. It entails a comparison between the terms (or features) present in the user's query and those found in the indexed documents. This subsystem not only assesses the similarity or relevance between the query and the documents; however, it also establishes the foundation for ranking and retrieving the most relevant results. Although this process is complex, it is essential because it enhances the effectiveness of information retrieval.

HISTORY AND EVOLUTION

Pre-computer era

It can be unambiguously asserted that cataloguing serves as the primordial soup for the emergence of Information Retrieval. In earlier times, various types of materials—such as books, documents, sacred manuscripts, scriptures, epics and spiritual texts—were preserved and indexed through cataloguing schemes. Eliot and Rose contended that in the 3rd century B.C., the Greek poet Callimachus first devised his own cataloguing systems to manage personal collections. During antiquity, several substantial libraries were established; for instance, the library at Alexandria (280 B.C.) housed over 700,000 documents. Nalanda University also boasted a massive library dedicated to document storage. However, the presence of any systematic mechanism to organize, classify, or retrieve these items remains unknown, because the historical record is rather vague on this point. Although significant advancements in cataloguing occurred, the fundamental essence of such organization has yet to be fully understood.

In 1891, Rudolph submitted a patent application to the US Patent Office for a machine that consisted of catalogue cards (which were) linked together. This (innovative device) could be wound past a viewing window, allowing for rapid manual scanning of the catalogues. However, Soper, in 1918, filed another patent for a device that aligned catalogue cards (with holes), corresponding to categories, in front of each other. This arrangement was designed to determine if there were entries in a collection that matched a specific combination of

categories. If light was visible through the configuration of cards, a match was identified.

The necessity of designing certain mechanical devices (which can be utilized for searching a catalogue) for a specific entry was felt over the years. Emanuel Goldberg was the first individual who endeavoured to address this issue in the 1920s and '30s, however, he did so indigenously. By nature, it is an optical device that essentially searches for a pattern of dots or letters within catalogues on (a roll of) microfilm. Goldberg patented numerous inventions in the field of photography, but his contributions went beyond that, because they laid the groundwork for future developments in information retrieval. Figure 1 shows the diagram of the patent filed in USPTO in 1928. "Here it can be seen that catalogue entries were stored on a roll of film (figure 1). A query (2) was also on film showing a negative image of the part of the catalogue being searched for; in this case the 1st and 6th entries on the roll. A light source (7) was shone through the catalogue roll and query film, focused onto a photocell (6). If an exact match was found, all light was blocked to the cell causing a relay to move a counter forward (12) and for an image of the match to be shown via a half-silvered mirror (3), reflecting the match onto a screen or photographic plate (4 & 5)".

Fig.1: Goldman Optical Machine (*Introduction to information retrieval – Information storage and retrieval.* (n.d.). <https://ebooks.inflibnet.ac.in/lisp7/chapter/chapter-1/>)

Following this significant invention (which occurred in 1935), Davis and Draeger conducted numerous experiments along a similar trajectory focused on microfilm-based searching. According to Mooers, their endeavours' had a profound impact on Vannevar Bush, leading to the development of the renowned Memex (Memory Expansion) System in 1945. However, one must consider the broader implications of their research; this was a pivotal moment in information retrieval. Although it may seem like a small step in hindsight, it laid the groundwork for future advancements.

Radolph Shaw implemented the Rapid Selector within the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) library. This machine was developed under the guidance of engineers at MIT, who worked on an earlier version of Rapid Selector with the consent of Vannevar Bush—delivering it to the USDA in 1949. It was reported that the machine could search through a 2,000-foot reel of film. Each half of the film's frames served a distinct purpose: one half for "frames of material," while the other half was designated for "index entries." It is stated that 72,000 frames were stored on the film, which, in total, were indexed by 430,000 entries. Shaw claimed that the selector could search at an impressive rate of 78,000 entries per minute. However, the effectiveness of this technology was not without its challenges, because the sheer volume of data required careful management. Although the system was groundbreaking, it also faced scrutiny regarding its efficiency and accuracy.

In 1950, Luhn (who was a pioneer in the field) also developed a selector that utilized punch cards, light and photo cells; this system could search through over 600 cards per minute. Another significant feature of this system is that it could identify the patterns of consecutive characters within a lengthy string. Calvin Mooers, during a conference in 1950, was the first to coin the term "Information Retrieval." However, the implications of this term were not fully understood at the time, although it laid the groundwork for future advancements in the field.

Early Use of Computers

The concept of utilizing computers to locate pertinent information gained significant traction through Vannevar Bush's article, "As We May Think," published in 1945. It appears that Bush drew inspiration from patents for a 'statistical machine'—which Emanuel Goldberg filed during the 1920s and '30s—that was designed to search for documents archived on film. The earliest account

of a computer engaged in information searching can be attributed to Holmstrom in 1948, who provided an initial reference to the Univac computer. Automated information retrieval systems emerged in the 1950s; one even made an appearance in the romantic comedy, *Desk Set*, released in 1957. In the 1960s, Gerard Salton established the first large-scale information retrieval research group at Cornell. By the 1970s, multiple retrieval techniques had demonstrated effectiveness on small text corpora, such as the Cranfield collection (comprising several thousand documents). Large-scale retrieval systems, like the Lockheed Dialog system, began to be implemented in the early 1970s. In 1992, the US Department of Defence, in conjunction with the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), cosponsored the Text Retrieval Conference (TREC) as part of the TIPSTER text program. The aim of this study was to investigate (or look into) the information retrieval community by providing the necessary infrastructure for evaluating text retrieval methodologies on an extensive text collection. This catalysed research on methods that can scale to enormous corpora. However, the advent of web search engines has greatly amplified the demand for large-scale retrieval systems.

Keyword-Based Search Engines

The advent (of) the World Wide Web in the 1990s signified a crucial milestone in the evolution of information retrieval; however, with the proliferation of online content, the need for effective search tools became paramount. Keyword-based search engines—such as AltaVista, Yahoo! and later Google—emerged as dominant players in this field, revolutionizing how users accessed (and) navigated the web. These search engines relied on algorithms that analysed keywords and meta-tags to rank and retrieve relevant web pages. Although this innovation has transformed the landscape, challenges remain because the sheer volume of content can complicate retrieval efforts.

The Rise of AI-Powered Search Engines

In recent years, the emergence of artificial intelligence (AI) has significantly altered the realm of information retrieval (once again). AI-driven search engines utilize machine learning algorithms, natural language processing (NLP) and various other techniques to comprehend user inquiries in a more sophisticated and contextual way. These advanced systems can analyse the semantics and intent behind a query; thus, they can provide more precise and tailored search results. However, this transformation comes with challenges, because not all

users may benefit equally. Although these technologies advance rapidly, there are still limitations that need to be addressed.

Semantic Search and Natural Language Understanding

One of the principal innovations introduced by AI search engines is semantic search (which goes beyond mere keyword matching) to comprehend the meaning and context of words and phrases within a query. By analysing the semantics of the language, these systems can infer the underlying intent behind a query—enabling them to surface more relevant and contextually appropriate results. Natural Language Understanding (NLU) capabilities, furthermore, enhance the user experience because they allow for more conversational and intuitive interactions with the search engine. However, this complexity can sometimes lead to unexpected outcomes, although the overall effectiveness is often improved.

TIMELINE

- Before the **1900s**

1801: Joseph Marie Jacquard invents the Jacquard loom, the first machine to use punched cards to control a sequence of operations.

1880s: Herman Hollerith invents an electro-mechanical data tabulator using punch cards as a machine readable medium.

1890 Hollerith cards, keypunches and tabulators used to process the 1890 US Census data.

- **1920s–1930s**

Emanuel Goldberg submits patents for his "Statistical Machine", a document search engine that used photoelectric cells and pattern recognition to search the metadata on rolls of microfilmed documents.

- **1940s–1950s**

late 1940s: The US military confronted problems of indexing and retrieval of wartime scientific research documents captured from Germans.

1945: Vannevar Bush's *As We May Think* appeared in *Atlantic Monthly*.

1947: Hans Peter Luhn (research engineer at IBM since 1941) began work on a mechanized punch card-based system for searching chemical compounds.

1950s: Growing concern in the US for a "science gap" with the USSR motivated, encouraged funding and provided a backdrop for mechanized literature searching systems and the invention of the citation index by Eugene Garfield.

1950: The term "information retrieval" was coined by Calvin Mooers.

1951:

- Philip Bagley conducted the earliest experiment in computerized document retrieval in a master thesis at MIT.
- Co-ordinate and UNITERM Indexing by Mortimer Taube

1955: Allen Kent joined Case Western Reserve University, and eventually became associate director of the Centre for Documentation and Communications Research. That same year, Kent and colleagues published a paper in American Documentation describing the precision and recall measures as well as detailing a proposed "framework" for evaluating an IR system which included statistical sampling methods for determining the number of relevant documents not retrieved.

1957: Cranfield 1 study by ASLIB under the supervision of C.W. Cleverdon using UNITERM and other classification systems (Universal Decimal Classification, Alphabetical Subject Catalogue, Faceted Classification Scheme). The main objective of the experiment centred around the investigation of

- i. The Cost of Indexing
- ii. The cost of preparing the physical index
- iii. The cost of searching

1958: International Conference on Scientific Information Washington DC included consideration of IR systems as a solution to problems identified.

1959: Hans Peter Luhn published "Auto-encoding of documents for information retrieval".

- **1960s:**

early 1960s: Gerard Salton began work on IR at Harvard, later moved to Cornell.

Gerard Salton proposed vector-space model for Information Retrieval and the performance of retrieval and ranking of the result was measured by cosine coefficient of document and query vector.

1960: Melvin Earl Maron and John Lary Kuhns published "On relevance, probabilistic indexing, and information retrieval" in the Journal of the ACM 7(3):216–244, July 1960.

1962:

- Cyril W. Cleverdon published early findings of the Cranfield studies, developing a model for IR system evaluation. See: Cyril W. Cleverdon, "Report on the Testing and Analysis of an Investigation into the Comparative Efficiency of Indexing Systems". Cranfield Collection of Aeronautics, Cranfield, England, 1962.
- Kent published *Information Analysis and Retrieval*.

1963:

- Weinberg report (1963) "Science, Government and Information" identified the problem of information transfer process and managing growing number of information along with its crisis. The report also put forward the urgency to address and formulate advanced techniques to retrieve information and manage and store them with convenience. This report made recommendations separately for Technical Community and Government Agencies.
- Joseph Becker and Robert M. Hayes published text on information retrieval. Becker, Joseph; Hayes, Robert Mayo. *Information storage and retrieval: tools, elements, theories*. New York, Wiley (1963).
- Cranfield—WRU test (Parallel to Cranfield-1 test)
 - Cranfield-2 test (1963-1966) was executed by C.W. Cleverdon, Mills and Keen and evaluated on the basis of two measures – Recall and Precision. Though, recall and precision measures were also used in Cranfield-WRU test.

1964:

- Karen Sparck Jones finished her thesis at Cambridge, *Synonymy and Semantic Classification*, and continued work on computational linguistics as it applies to IR.
- The National Bureau of Standards sponsored a symposium titled "Statistical Association Methods for Mechanized Documentation". Several highly significant papers, including G. Salton's first published reference (we believe) to the SMART system.

1965: J. C. R. Licklider published *Libraries of the Future*.

1966: Don Swanson was involved in studies at University of Chicago on Requirements for Future Catalogues.

1966-67

During 1966-67, F.W. Lancaster evaluated the MEDLARS (Medical Literature Analysis and Retrieval System) Demand Search Service. MEDLARS eventually gave birth to AIM-TWX and he also evaluated that during 1970-71. MEDLARS and AIM-TWX were the previous versions of MEDLINE/PubMed.

late 1960s: F. Wilfrid Lancaster completed evaluation studies of the MEDLARS system and published the first edition of his text on information retrieval.

1968:

- Gerard Salton published *Automatic Information Organization and Retrieval*.
- John W. Sammon, Jr.'s RADC Tech report "Some Mathematics of Information Storage and Retrieval..." outlined the vector model.
- In 1968, the project report was published on the Intrex database design in MIT. This system could read the machine readable flexible, analytically-structured, catalogue-record format. Effort was also given "to the creation from each document of a set of complete index term phrases and to the problems of matching these unconstrained terms with similarly unconstrained subject request phrases".
- SMART (System for the Mechanical Analysis and Retrieval of Text) Information Retrieval system developed by the leadership of Gerard Salton in Cornell University in 1960s. This system incorporated many important concepts like vector space model, relevance feedback, and

Rocchio Classification. In 1968, Salton published his famous book titled as "Automatic Information Organization and Retrieval"

- J.W. Sammon (1969) gave the idea of visualisation interface integrated to an IR system in his famous paper "A nonlinear mapping for data structure analysis".

1969: Sammon's "A nonlinear mapping for data structure analysis Archived 2017-08-08 at the Wayback Machine" (IEEE Transactions on Computers) was the first proposal for visualization interface to an IR system.

- **1970s**

early 1970s:

- First online systems—NLM's AIM-TWX, MEDLINE; Lockheed's Dialog; SDC's ORBIT.
- Theodor Nelson promoting concept of hypertext, published *Computer Lib/Dream Machines*.

1971: Nicholas Jardine and Cornelis J. van Rijsbergen published "The use of hierarchic clustering in information retrieval", which articulated the "cluster hypothesis".

1975: Three highly influential publications by Salton fully articulated his vector processing framework and term discrimination model:

- A Theory of Indexing (Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics)
- A Theory of Term Importance in Automatic Text Analysis (JASIS v. 26)
- A Vector Space Model for Automatic Indexing (CACM 18:11)

1978: ACM SIGIR Conference started in 1978 which subsequently emerged as the apex conference in this field.

1979: C. J. van Rijsbergen published *Information Retrieval* (Butterworths). Heavy emphasis on probabilistic models.

1979: Tamas Doszkocs implemented the CITE natural language user interface for MEDLINE at the National Library of Medicine. The CITE system supported free form query input, ranked output and relevance feedback.

- **1980s**

1980: First international ACM SIGIR conference, joint with British Computer Society IR group in Cambridge.

1982:

- Nicholas J. Belkin, Robert N. Oddy, and Helen M. Brooks proposed the ASK (Anomalous State of Knowledge) viewpoint for information retrieval. This was an important concept, though their automated analysis tool proved ultimately disappointing.
- One important invention happened during 1982-88 was formulation OKAPI model. It was developed at polytechnic of Central London. Okapi is a set-oriented ranked output design for probabilistic type retrieval of textual material using inverted index.

1983: Salton (and Michael J. McGill) published *Introduction to Modern Information Retrieval* (McGraw-Hill), with heavy emphasis on vector models.

1985: David Blair and Bill Maron publish: *An Evaluation of Retrieval Effectiveness for a Full-Text Document-Retrieval System*

mid-1980s: Efforts to develop end-user versions of commercial IR systems.

1985–1993: Key papers on and experimental systems for visualization interfaces.

Work by Donald B. Crouch, Robert R. Korfhage, Matthew Chalmers, Anselm Spoerri and others.

1989: First World Wide Web proposals by Tim Berners-Lee at CERN.

- **1990s**

1992: TREC conference started as part of TIPSTER text program in 1992 and it was sponsored by US Defence and National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST).

1996:

- PageRank algorithm was developed at Stanford University by Larry Page and Sergey Brin.
- Latent Dirichlet allocation (LDA), a generative/topic model in NLP was developed by David Blei, Andrew NG, and Michael Jordan in 2003. LDA is similar to Probabilistic Latent Semantic Analysis (PLSA) and Latent

Semantic Indexing (LSI). LSI gained huge popularity in WWW and was hugely used in Search Engine Optimization (SEO).

1997:

- Publication of Korfhage's *Information Storage and Retrieval* with emphasis on visualization and multi-reference point systems.
- Google Inc. was born which has now ruling dominantly in searching engine domain.

1999: Publication of Ricardo Baeza-Yates and Berthier Ribeiro-Neto's *Modern Information Retrieval* by Addison Wesley, the first book that attempts to cover all IR.

late 1990s: Web search engines implementation of many features formerly found only in experimental IR systems. Search engines become the most common and maybe best instantiation of IR models.

Major conferences

- SIGIR: Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval
- ECIR: European Conference on Information Retrieval
- CIKM: Conference on Information and Knowledge Management
- WWW: International World Wide Web Conference
- WSDM: Conference on Web Search and Data Mining
- ICTIR: International Conference on Theory of Information Retrieval

AWARDS IN THE FIELD

- Tony Kent Strix award
- Gerard Salton Award
- Karen Sparck Jones Award

CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Although significant advancements have been achieved in AI-powered search engines, several challenges persist (this remains a pressing concern). Issues such as bias in algorithms, privacy concerns and the need for transparency and explainability in AI continue to pose ongoing obstacles for the field of information retrieval. Furthermore, because the volume and complexity of digital information are expanding, there exists a constant requirement for innovation and adaptation within search technology. Looking ahead, the future of information retrieval will likely be shaped by advancements in AI, natural language processing and other emerging technologies. Deep learning techniques—including neural networks and deep reinforcement learning—hold considerable promise for enhancing the accuracy and relevance of search results. However, developments in voice search, augmented reality and virtual assistants are expected to redefine how users interact with and retrieve information in the years to come.

CONCLUSION

The evolution of information retrieval has been characterized by constant innovation and the necessity to adapt to the shifting needs and demands of users. From the early manual cataloguing systems to contemporary AI-driven search engines, the trajectory of information retrieval illustrates the relentless pursuit for more efficient, accurate and personalized means to access and navigate the expansive ocean of digital information. As technology progresses, the future of information retrieval, however, holds thrilling possibilities for further enhancing how we discover, consume and interact with information in the digital era. This is important, because the ways in which we engage with information are continually evolving. Although challenges remain, the potential for advancements is immense, but the journey is far from over.

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